

Data Management Plan (DMP)

A DMP is a valuable tool designed to help you prepare for effective data management in the research process. It also serves as a checklist to ensure that important aspects of data handling are addressed during the research project and in the long term after its completion. Nearly all funding institutions now require a DMP, either already as part of a grant application or for approved projects.

As a dynamic, 'living' document, a DMP should be as concise as possible. Numerous templates and online tools are available to assist you in the development of your DMP.

A DMP usually provides information on the following aspects:

Data collection & documentation <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Data type, format and volume• Reuse of data• Collection standards and methods• File organization and versioning• Documentation and metadata	Ethical, legal & security issues <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Data protection• Data security• Copyright issues• Research ethics
Data storage & preservation <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Storage location & capacity• Backup• Responsibilities• Planning and selection of data for archiving	Data exchange & reuse <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Access/publication• Repositories

DMP templates by the University of Basel:

On the website of the Research Data Management Network, you can find templates for writing DMPs in life sciences and humanities: <https://researchdata.unibas.ch/en/planning/dmp>

DMP Tools

- [ARGOS](#)
- [Data Stewardship Wizard](#) and [DS Wizard of the SIB](#)
- [DMPTool](#)
- [DMPonline](#) | [DCC](#)
- [RDMO GitHub](#)

By starting data management planning early in your project, you can...:

- assign clear roles and responsibilities for data management within your team.
- estimate necessary infrastructure, services, legal advice, and budget requirements (sometimes reimbursable by your funder).
- identify open questions concerning your data that may need clarification during later project phases.
- increase research efficiency, saving time and resources in the long run.
- prevent loss of data by enhancing data security.
- avoid data duplication through effective data organization.
- establish continuity by ensuring that new project members can easily orient themselves through well-organized data and thorough documentation.
- boost the visibility and outreach of your research data through data publication.
- enhance the reproducibility and verifiability of your research.

